

THE STUDY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PETANQUE SPORT IN CENTRAL JAVA PROVINCE INDONESIA

ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ РОЗВИТКУ ПЕТАНК СПОРТУ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНІЙ ПРОВІНЦІЇ ЯВА В ІНДОНЕЗІЇ

Ganang Pamungkas Wicaksana Jananta, Agus Kristiyanto, Muchsin Doewes

Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia

Abstract

This study aims to determine: 1) The development of petanque sports in Central Java Province, 2) The socialization efforts of the Petanque sport implemented by the Central Java Provincial Government, 3) Coaching of petanque sports achievements in Central Java Province. The place or location of the research is the Indonesian Petanque Sports Federation (FOPI Central Java Government). This research is a type of case study research. This research uses qualitative methods, namely observation, interviews, or document review. There are three data analysis activities that must be carried out, namely data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions or verification. Based on the research results, the following conclusions can be drawn: 1) The development of petanque sports in Central Java is very rapid. 2) Petanque Central Java. 3) The Petanque Central Java Organizational Structure is good. 4) The coordination between FOPI officials in Central Java is good. 5) The management of FOPI Central Java has the responsibility and obligation to provide guidance to all cities / regencies. 6) The management of the Central Java FOPI province has made efforts to hold as many events as possible to recruit talented athletes, hold trainers and referees upgrading. 7) Socialization of petanque sports is still being carried out by introducing petanque sports to schools by involving teachers, elementary, junior high, high school and university students are the main targets in socialization. 8) The development of petanque athletes in Central Java is in a good category. 9) Organizational performance, the role of socialization, and overall petanque sports coaching are going well.

Key words: Development Studies, Petanque Sports.

Це дослідження має на меті визначити: 1) розвиток петанк спорту в провінції Центральна Ява; 2) зусилля з соціалізації петанк спорту, реалізовані урядом провінції Центральна Ява; 3) тренування спортивних досягнень петанк в провінції Центральна Ява. Місцем локалізації проведення дослідження є Індонезійська федерація спорту петанк (Федерація петанку Індонезії, Уряд Центральної Яви). Це дослідження є різновидом тематичного дослідження. У цьому дослідженні використовуються якісні методи, а саме спостереження, інтерв'ю або огляд документів. Здійснено три етапи аналізу даних, а саме скорочення даних, представлення даних та складання висновків або перевірку. На основі результатів дослідження можна зробити такі висновки: 1) Розвиток спорту з петанку в Центральній Яві відбувається дуже швидко. 2) Петанк Центральна Ява. 3) Організаційна структура Центральної Яви Петанку хороша. 4) Координація між посадовими особами Федерації петанку Індонезії в Центральній Яві є хорошою. 5) Керівництво Федерації петанку Індонезії в Центральній Яві несе відповідальність та зобов'язання надавати керівництво всім містам / регіонам. 6) Керівництво Федерації петанку Індонезії в Центральній Яві доклало зусиль для проведення якомога більшої кількості заходів для залучення талановитих спортсменів, проведення тренерів та арбітрів для підвищення кваліфікації. 7) Соціалізація спорту з петанку все ще проводиться шляхом впровадження спорту з петанку у школах шляхом залучення вчителів, учнів початкових класів, молодших школярів та студентів вищих навчальних закладів є головними цілями соціалізації. 8) Розвиток спортсменів з петанку в Центральній Яві знаходиться в хорошій категорії. 9) Організаційні показники, роль соціалізації та загальне тренування з петанку в спорті йдуть добре.

Ключові слова: дослідження розвитку, петанк спорт.

Introduction. Petanque is a form of boules game where the goal is to throw an iron ball as close as possible to a wooden ball called a jack and the feet must be in a small circle which is often called a circle (Sutrisna et al., 2018). This game is usually played on hard ground, but can also be played on grass, sand or other ground surfaces (Juhanis et al., 2017). Petanque in several countries

is a tool of communicating a study which states the importance of having social interaction and petanque has benefited him from social aspects. Petanque has various names that differ in each country (Pilus et al., 2017). Bocee is the title of petanque sport in Turkey and Bowls is a designation in the UK (Eler & Eler, 2018). Bocci is a sport in the family of boules, a type of game played with metal balls (Loser et al., 2011).

Petanque sport began to be known in Indonesia starting from 2002 after previously being officially competed at the Malaysian Sea Games in 2001 (Sinaga & Ibrahim, 2019). Petanque sports in Indonesia with the formation of the Indonesian Petanque Sports Federation (FOPI) which is the parent organization of petanque in Indonesia (Pramono, 2017). The 26th Sea Games which was held in Palembang was the first time Indonesia participated in the petanque sport (Okilanda et al., 2018). The Sea Games 2015 in Singapore is the highest achievement of the Indonesian petanque sport in this Southeast Asian sports championship by winning 1 silver medal. Petanque sports are easy sports and can be played by anyone (Agustina & Priambodo, 2017). Petanque is a sport that can be played by all ages from young to old people because in this sport it is not required to perform difficult movements and requires a lot of energy (Widodo & Hafidz, 2018). Petanque has a tendency to experience very small injuries so that it is safer to be played by small children and even people who are already in the elderly (Bustomi et al., 2020).

Sports coaching can be carried out from the region or province as the vanguard in advancing national sports achievements (Suwiwa, 2015). Parent sports in each province are expected to pay more attention to and organize in a planned, systematic, and manage professionally every form of sports implementation (Saputra et al., 2019). Clarity and decisiveness in the division of tasks, responsibilities and authorities between the Government and Regional Governments can increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the administration of government affairs, the quality of public services in the field of sports and the development of regional superior potential through community participation, as well as concrete steps to optimize the potential for local excellence as a driving force to improve national sports achievements (Okilanda, 2018).

Petanque is a promising new sport because the total number of contested numbers is quite a lot, namely 11 numbers under athletics with 47 numbers and swimming with 40 numbers (Hondri, 2020). There needs to be intensive attention for the petanque sport so that in the future it will develop and become one of the leading sports that become a medal contributor in the National level championships for Central Java.

Methods. This research is an evaluative study with a context, input, process, product (CIPP) model. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling technique. Data collection techniques in this evaluative research are observation and questionnaires (questionnaires). The method used in this research is a questionnaire method using a Likert scale. The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive analysis by describing and interpreting the data from each component being evaluated.

Results and Discussion

1. Performance of the Petanque Sports Organization in Central Java Province

All sports activities in order to achieve the goals to be achieved by a sports club require the formation of a good and planned organization. For this reason, a sports organization must fulfill the elements as a sports organization, so that it can create a sport that is healthy, good and runs smoothly so as to achieve the desired goals.

Petanque sports entered Central Java Province in 2015, the management of FOPI Central Java was inaugurated by the General Chairperson of the Indonesian Petanque Sports Federation (PB FOPI) Mr. Caca Isa Saleh based on the General Chair's Decree on January 9th, 2016 at Tunas Pembangunan University, Surakarta. The management of FOPI Central Java is dominated by academics in the field of sports such as lecturers, teachers, and sports students. The leadership of FOPI Central Java for the 2016-2020 period was held by Dr. Taufiq Hidayah, M.Kes as General Chairperson and Mr. Sri Haryono, S.Pd., M.Or as Daily Chair. The Secretariat of the Petanque Indonesia Sports Federation of Central Java Province (FOPI Jawa Tengah) is located in the Jati Diri stadium complex, Semarang. FOPI Central Java is one of the sports organizations engaged in the development of petanque sports in Central Java.

a. Organizational Structure

Structure is one of the most important factors in an organization, which shows the functions or positions of the organization and how they are related to each other.

FOPI Central Java was officially inaugurated by the General Chairperson of the Indonesian Petanque Sports Federation (PB FOPI) based on Decree No: 03-SK / FOPI / 2016 concerning the Inauguration of Personnel for the Indonesian Petanque Sports Federation, Central Java Province

for the 2016-2020 Service Period. The first Central Java FOPI management was led by Dr. Taufiq Hidayah, M.Kes. as General Chair.

For the structure of petanque sports in Central Java for 3 years (from 2015 to 2017), although some people who hold positions in provincial management are not people who live in Semarang. However, it is still able to run well and significantly, because of quality human resources and the formation of management in the regency cities of Central Java province.

b. Coordination

The implementation of work programs that have been mutually agreed at members work meetings in FOPI Central Java, carried out with coordination between the management. The coordination that can be carried out can be in the form of coordination in each sector which is then continued to the inter-sectoral coordination meeting up to the highest, namely the coordination meeting of all FOPI administrators in Central Java. The coordination meeting in each field is scheduled by internal members in that field according to the needs of the activity. Routine management meeting 1 year 1 time, but if an event is to be held then it can be 4 to 6 times.

c. Organizational Design

FOPI Central Java designed the development of petanque sports with has the responsibility and obligation to provide guidance in the development of petanque sports in all district cities in Central Java. Conducting outreach provides non-formal insights to people who want to study petanque sports.

In the design of petanque sports in all corners of the Central Java region, it requires the role of administrators, both from provincial administrators and from district city administrators in Central Java province. Government of Central Java Province FOPI and coaches conduct a TC (Training Camp) program for athletes who will take part in the National Championship, then schedule a try in or try out to other provinces, to monitor the mental development of athletes before competing. So far, Central Java FOPI has only tried in the provinces of West Java and East Java.

d. Authority, Power, and Influence

In every Regional Championship tournament or even National open tournament held by the Provincial Management (Pengprov), then the authority is in Government of FOPI Central Java. The Central Java coach monitors to find out the

progress of athletes in participating in the championships and get seeds to compete in the official National championships and become a strength for the province of Central Java.

e. Innovation

Government of FOPI Central Java conducts outreach to schools, organizes events for senior and junior levels, so that there is continuous continuity, and upgrading of coaches and referees at the regional level. The development of petanque sports in Central Java Province with the formation of the management of FOPI district cities, so that petanque sports can be included in the sports that are competed in PORPROV Central Java.

2. Socialization

Socialization is one of the most important parts in the success of a program. This is important because socialization is an effort to introduce or disseminate information about petanque sports to educating communities (sports teachers) and other communities as well as to agencies or supporting institutions in Central Java Province.

Petanque sports began to enter and be known in Central Java starting from the socialization which was held on September 15th, 2015. The socialization of petanque sports was held in collaboration between Semarang State University and PB FOPI. Important figures for the entry and development of petanque sports in Central Java, namely Mr. Rivan Saghita Pratama, S.Pd., M.Or and Mr. Dr. Ramdan Pelana, M.Or who served as PB FOPI Deputy of General Secretary. The socialization that was carried out became the beginning of the development of petanque sports and the formation of the Regional Management of Petanque sports in Central Java.

Activities carried out by FOPI Central Java are socializing, introducing, developing, and increasing the achievements of Central Java petanque sports at the national and international levels. Central Java FOPI has a tough task because it has to introduce and socialize the petanque sport which is a new sport in Indonesia. Outreach activities to regions and providing training to sports teachers are the first steps taken by FOPI Central Java as an effort to socialize petanque sports.

Central Java FOPI must move quickly to develop and prepare for the petanque championships in the near future. Petanque sport

is classified as a new sport, but major championships have competed petanque sports. National and international championships or sports events have competed in the petanque sport. The 2015 National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) in Aceh already competed a petanque sports exhibition, which was attended by 14 provinces. The championship which was held in 2016 was an exhibition for the petanque sport at the XIX National Sports Week (PON) in West Java. In 2017, Central Java Province sent its athletes to participate in the Student Sports Week (POMNAS) in Makassar. Central Java athletes in petanque sports managed to get 2 gold and 2 bronze medals. In 2018 Central Java athletes participated in the National Sports Week (PON) selection which would determine their next steps in order to compete in the official PON event in Papua. Furthermore, in 2019 the Petanque Athletes of Central Java will take part in a grand event which is held every 2 years, namely the National Student Sports Week (POMNAS) Event in West Java.

Public perceptions of petanque sports are very diverse, some are interested, some are slightly interested, and some are not even interested. People think that petanque sports have many advantages and superiority. First, this sport is individual and competes for medals of 11 to 13 numbers, so that by fostering a relatively small number of players, they can participate in 11 numbers. The coaching budget is certainly more affordable. Apart from that, the procurement of facilities and infrastructure is also very easy and cheap. But in plain view, petanque sports do not require too much physical, so many people think that petanque sports are less challenging.

3. Sports Achievement Coaching

Coaching with the right pattern will be able to develop the potential of an athlete. To develop achievements, coaching is needed in an integrated, directed and sustainable manner and starting at an early age or at a young age. The stages required in sports of achievement are the implementation stage which includes training, nursery, development of achievement. Meanwhile, coaching in petanque sports in Central Java Province is in accordance with good coaching, and considers that the role of the coach is very influential in improving athlete achievement, so that the coaching carried out is not only from the administrators but the coach also plays an

important role in coaching. The stages of coaching are as follows:

a. Developing massively

Efforts made to improve or add to sports petanque athletes in Central Java Province is to hold regular matches each month, from regional competitions in Central Java Province for senior and junior levels, to open tournaments held by each district / city in Central Java Province. This is to attract the attention and interest of people who see or watch, and attract new, competent athletes.

Apart from the tournament, the administrators of Central Java Province also monitor athletes while playing or after the match is over. This is to measure the ability of athletes, look for potential athletes, monitored for 2 to 3 weeks or even 2 to 3 months if there is a significant improvement and development in terms of technique, then they can follow the next stage to become a petanque athlete in the Province Central Java in the national championship.

b. Nursery

To get potential athletes, management of FOPI Central Java, opens and provides the widest possible opportunity for all athletes to develop the playing talents of each athlete. FOPI Central Java has several petanque sports clubs or associations as a place for training the seeds of Central Java petanque athletes.

FOPI Central Java holds activities to conduct regional selection to bring athletes to compete in national level championships. After the selection is held, the athletes take part in a training camp in preparation for the National Championship. This proves that FOPI Central Java is not only participating in the National Championship, but is able to compete with other provinces and also has targets that must be achieved in the National Championship.

c. Achievement Development

Sports coaching is an existing foundation with the aim of achieving achievement in the world of sports. The coaching process is a long and systematic series involving all aspects related to sports. Sports clubs or associations are the origin of sports, which are the starting place for the formation of young athletes who will later be fostered into high achieving athletes. Coaching must be well planned starting from sports clubs and societies. The training process that is carried out must be well programmed and always evaluate the progress of the training process. FOPI

Central Java has provided an overview of the training program that must be carried out in Petanque sports clubs and associations.

FOPI Central Java has sent its athletes, both senior and junior, to several national petanque championships. Central Java junior petanque athletes have not received satisfactory results when participating in the junior petanque National Championship. Senior athletes have participated in several national level championships such as POMNAS XIX Aceh 2015, National Sports Week Exhibition (PON) XIX West Java 2016, POMNAS XX Makassar 2017, Pra PON 2018 West Java, and POMNAS 2019 Jakarta. The highest achievement for Central Java petanque athletes always increases from each championship that is followed in the National event.

Conclusion. Based on the results of research on the Petanque Sport Development Study in Central Java Province from 2015 to 2019, the following conclusions can be drawn as a whole:

1. The development of petanque sports in Central Java is very rapid. In just five years, 22 out of 35 districts have formed a management at the city / district level and more than 500 people are actively involved in petanque sports activities.

2. Petanque Central Java has a good organization, namely FOPI Central Java which was legalized through Decree No: 03 - SK / FOPI / 2016 concerning the Inauguration of Personnel for the Indonesian Petanque Sports Federation, Central Java Province for the 2016 - 2020 Service Period.

3. The Petanque Central Java organizational structure is good. It is proven that in a period of 5 years (2015 to 2019) they have carried out the main tasks and functions in each field.

4. Coordination between Central Java FOPI administrators has been good, carried out through each sector, then conveyed through routine meetings that are held once a year, but if an event is to be held then it can be 4 to 6 coordination meetings.

5. In the development of petanque sports in the province of Central Java, the management of

FOPI Central Java has the responsibility and obligation to provide guidance in all cities / districts and this has been proven well with the current 22 management at the city / regency level.

6. FOPI Central Java provincial administrators have made efforts to hold as many events as possible to attract talented athletes, holding trainers and referees as well as one of the innovations made by the FOPI Central Java provincial administrators.

7. Socialization of petanque sports is still being carried out by introducing petanque sports to schools by involving teachers both in learning and in MGMP activities. Elementary, junior high, high school and university students are the main targets in socialization, to encourage the Central Java FOPI administrators to routinely hold competition events as a means of measuring training results and achieving achievements.

8. Development of petanque athletes in Central Java is in a good category. Petanque Central Java has clubs and associations that already have club legality in the form of AD / ART as well as club management arrangements, namely Unnes Petanque Club and UTP Petanque Club. Training program guidelines have been made to be carried out in each club which is then reported as material for evaluating the existing coaching at the existing Petanque clubs and associations. Petanque Central Java has sent its athletes to several national and international petanque championships. The achievements of FOPI Central Java are extraordinary, this is evident in the past 5 years that Central Java FOPI athletes have managed to make very proud achievements both in national and international events.

9. Petanque Central Java, when viewed from 3 aspects of development: organizational performance, the role of socialization, and sports achievement coaching, illustrates that petanque as a new sport can develop rapidly and support the achievements of Central Java sports.

References

1. Agustina, A. T., & Priambodo, A. (2017). Hubungan Antara Tingkat Konsentrasi Terhadap Hasil Ketepatan Shooting Olahraga Petanque Pada Peserta Unesa Petanque Club. *Pendidikan Olahraga Dan Kesehatan*.

2. Bustomi, A. O., Hidayah, T., Okilanda, A., & Putra, D. D. (2020). Analisis Gerak Pointing Pada Olahraga Petanque. *Journal Sport Area*. [https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2020.vol5\(1\).4807](https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2020.vol5(1).4807)

3. Eler, N., & Eler, S. (2018). A Study on Somatotype Profiles of the Players in Turkish Bocce National Team. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v6i2.2940>
4. Juhanis, B. B., & Nur, M. (2017). Pelatihan Teknik Dasar dan Sosialisasi Peraturan Permainan Olahraga Petanque pada Mahasiswa FIK UNM Makassar. *Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat Universitas Negeri Makassar*.
5. Loser, R., Piskoty, G., Al-Badri, A., Tuchschnid, M., Schmid, P., & Leemann, A. (2011). Investigation into the mechanisms leading to explosion of pétanque balls. *Engineering Failure Analysis*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2010.09.029>
6. Okilanda, A. (2018). Revitalisasi Masyarakat Urban/Perkotaan Melalui Olahraga Petanque. *Halaman Olahraga Nusantara (Jurnal Ilmu Keolahragaan)*.
<https://doi.org/10.31851/hon.v1i1.1505>
7. Okilanda, A., Arisman, A., Lestari, H., Lanos, M. E. C., Fajar, M., Putri, S. A. R., & Sugarwanto, S. (2018). Sosialisasi Petanque Sebagai Olahraga Masa Kini. *JURNAL BAGIMU NEGERI*. <https://doi.org/10.26638/jbn.638.8651>
8. Pilus, A. M., Amin, M. N. M., Din, A., & Muhammad, N. (2017). The Effect of Sport Technology on Student- Athletes ' Petanque Skill Performance. *Applied Engineering Research*.
9. Pramono, H. (2017). View of Perspektif Olahraga Petanque dalam Mendukung Prestasi Olahraga Jawa Tengah. *Journal of Physical Education and Sports*.
10. Saputra, M. F. B., Kristiyanto, A., & Doewes, M. (2019). Management Analysis of Indonesian Petanque Federation Province (FOPI) Central Java in Supporting Sports Achievement in Indonesia. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*.
<https://doi.org/10.18415/ijmmu.v6i2.895>
11. Sinaga, F. S. G., & Ibrahim, I. (2019). Analysis biomechanics pointing dan shooting petanque pada atlet TC PON XX PAPUA. *Sains Olahraga: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Keolahragaan*.
12. Sutrisna, T., Asmawi, M., & Pelana, R. (2018). Model Latihan Keterampilan Shooting Olahraga Petanque Untuk Pemula. *JURNAL SEGAR*. <https://doi.org/10.21009/segar/0701.05>
13. Suwiwa, I. G. I. wayan A. I. M. A. W. (2015). Pelatihan Olahraga Petanque Bagi Guru SD, SMP SMA dan SMK se-Kabupaten Buleleng Tahun 2015. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*.
14. T.Hondri, H. S. (2020). Profil Manajemen Pembinaan Prestasi Nusantara Petanque Club Kota Kediri 2019-2020. *MOTION*.
15. Widodo, W., & Hafidz, A. (2018). Kontribusi Panjang Lengan, Koordinasi Mata Tangan, dan Konsentrasi Terhadap Ketepatan Shooting Pada Olahraga Petanque. *Prestasi Olahraga*.